

Metaplastic Carcinoma: Case Study and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT:

Metaplastic carcinoma, also known as breast carcinosarcoma, is a rare and aggressive tumor characterized by the presence of both epithelial and mesenchymal components. This article presents two cases of breast carcinosarcoma and provides a review of the literature, examining the radiological, clinical, histopathological, and therapeutic characteristics, which differ from those of the usual form of breast cancer.

Keywords: Breast carcinosarcoma, metaplastic sarcoma of the breast, biopsy, mammography, ultrasound, breast MRI.

INTRODUCTION:

Breast carcinosarcoma, also known as metaplastic sarcoma of the breast, accounts for less than 1% of all breast cancers. Its rarity and the mixed nature of its components make its diagnosis and management particularly complex. We discuss here an illustrative clinical case accompanied by a literature review to highlight this pathology with an unfavorable prognosis.

ovarian cancer and no history of hormone replacement therapy, consulted following self-palpation of a right breast mass. Clinical examination found an enlarged, red, and hot right breast with an orange peel appearance. Palpation revealed a central mass extending to the inner quadrant, measuring 12 cm/12 cm, poorly defined, hard, fixed, and painful, associated with inflammatory signs such as an erythematous plaque and orange peel skin without nipple discharge (Figure 1).

CASE OBSERVATION 1:

Mrs. B.N, a 55-year-old postmenopausal woman with no particular personal or family history of breast or

Figure 1. Central right breast mass with inflammatory phenomenon and skin ulceration.

Axillary and supraclavicular lymph node areas were negative. The stage was T4dN0M0. Mammography found a mass in the upper-inner quadrant, roughly oval-shaped with irregular contours without microcalcification foci (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Mammographic appearance of the central mass in the right breast, lobulated in shape.

Breast ultrasound showed the mass to be irregularly shaped, with microlobulated contours, heterogeneous solid and cystic (Figures 3 and 4), and vascularized on color Doppler.

Figure 3: Breast ultrasound. Mass with irregular shape, microlobulated heterogeneous contours, both solid and cystic.

Figure 4. Metaplastic squamous cell carcinoma. HXE10.i:squamous metaplasia with dyskeratotic cells .

This echomammographic appearance is classified as BI-RADS 5 by the ACR. Microbiopsies revealed an invasive ductal carcinoma, grade III, triple-negative, KI 67/60%. The extension assessment, including a thoraco-abdomino-pelvic CT scan, revealed 04 hepatic micronodules, one of which is cystic + hepatohilar lymphadenopathy 45x25 mm. An abdominal MRI also requested confirmed the absence of hepatic localization but showed hepatohilar lymphadenopathy masses (52x34 mm); bone scintigraphy was normal. The stage was T4dN0M1 Pev2. The patient was put on chemotherapy followed by radical surgery. L'histologie

a conclu à une prolifération tumorale maligne metaplasique de type épidermoïde . Il n'était pas vu de composante canalaire in situ ou d'embolies vasculaires, ni d'envahissement cutané. The resection boundaries were sound. Absence of lymph node metastases (0N+/20N). Progesterone and estrogen hormone receptors as well as the Hercept test were negative. Tumor cells expressed pankeratin AE1/3 and did not express CD34, P100, AML, and Desmin (Figure 4). The diagnosis was triple-negative primary invasive carcinosarcoma of the breast. The patient was referred for initial chemotherapy, and faced with the

progression of the disease. Cleanliness surgery was performed with radiotherapy.

DISCUSSION:

Breast carcinosarcoma is a complex malignant tumor composed of epithelial tissue (carcinoma) and malignant cells of mesenchymal origin (sarcoma). The term sarcomatoid metaplastic carcinoma is often used to describe this rare entity[1,2]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) classification of 2002-2003, carcinosarcoma falls within the group of metaplastic carcinomas[1]. This tumor is distinguished by its size, usually between 3 and 18 cm, and by a growth rate faster than that of other classic infiltrating carcinomas[3,4]. Macroscopically, it presents a larger size than that of infiltrating ductal carcinoma. The majority of carcinosarcomas are negative for estrogen and progesterone receptors, as well as for HER2-neu[5]. Histopathologically, carcinosarcoma can be confused with high-grade phyllodes tumors due to malignant transformation of the epithelial component.

CONCLUSION:

Breast carcinosarcoma remains a challenge in breast imaging due to its rarity, appearance, and the diverse mammographic and sonographic semiology. The case presented underscores the importance of early diagnosis and an adapted therapeutic strategy.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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This distinction is important for therapeutic and prognostic management[6]. The mammographic appearance is nonspecific. It most often presents as a poorly defined mass with irregular, sometimes spiculated, contours. Microcalcifications are rare. Ultrasound is more sensitive, showing the heterogeneous nature of the lesion, alternating between solid and cystic areas[7]. The treatment of breast carcinosarcoma follows the same principles as for other types of breast cancers, including mastectomy with or without axillary clearance. Wargotz and Norris reported a lymph node invasion rate of 26%, highlighting the importance of axillary clearance[8]. Standard chemotherapy is unsatisfactory, as chemoresistance is common[9]. Hormonotherapy usually has no role due to the typical absence of hormone receptor expression. Herceptin cannot be introduced in most cases, as the Herceptest is often negative. Post-treatment monitoring is essential to detect any early recurrence, given the high risk of metastasis associated with this type of cancer[10].

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